

Effect of different organic material on lead adsorption in soils of Aligarh district

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Abstract : The effect of different organic material (FYM, sewage sludge and poultry litter) on adsorption-desorption of lead on three soil samples of Aligarh district was studied. The adsorption isotherms were of 'L' type and adsorption-desorption data conformed to Freundlich isotherm equation. The adsorption increased with the increase in organic material and followed the order : sewage sludge > FYM > poultry litter. The adsorptivity of soils was in order : Soil No. 1 > 2 > 3. The adsorption capacity was significantly positively correlated with soil organic carbon and soil-clay-content. The desorption of lead was more by CaCl_2 than water and followed the order : soil 3 > 2 > 1. The desorption of lead decreased with the addition of organic material suggesting a less availability of lead to crops grown on such soils. The complete desorption of lead did not take place.

Keywords : Adsorption, desorption, lead, soils.

Introduction

The concentration of a metal in the soil solution and its potential toxicity are mostly controlled by adsorption-desorption reactions at the surface of both inorganic and organic soil colloidal materials¹. Lead is one of the chemical pollutants of the environment and is highly toxic to man as it inhibits many enzyme systems². Sorption of metals by soils is strongly influenced by various soil parameters, viz. pH, organic matter content, CEC, soil type and plant species³. Application of organic materials such as FYM, sewage sludge, poultry litter affect solubility or dissociation kinetics of heavy metals due to formation of various insoluble compounds in soil^{4,5}. This paper re-

ports the results of the study on adsorption-desorption behaviour of lead in Aligarh soils amended with different organic materials.

Results and discussion

Adsorption of lead : Freundlich adsorption equation was used to describe the lead adsorption on soil in presence and absence of different organic materials. The linear form of this equation is $\log X = \log K + 1/n \log C$, where X is amount of lead adsorbed per unit mass of soil (mg g^{-1} soil), C is equilibrium concentration in solution (mg mL^{-1}), K and $1/n$ are constants. K is the adsorption coefficient, $1/n$ is a describer of isotherm curvature. The

Table 1. Physico-chemical properties of the materials used under study

Characteristics	Soil 1	Soil 2	Soil 3	FYM	Sewage sludge	Poultry litter
	Alluvial (Typic Ustochrept)	Aridisol (Typic Orthids)	(Calciorthents)			
Soil (%)	38.8	44.9	24.9	-	-	-
Sand (%)	45.0	41.5	65.3	-	-	-
Clay	16.2	13.6	9.8	-	-	-
pH	7.8	7.4	8.3	7.9	7.6	6.9
EC (dSm^{-1})	0.38	0.29	0.26	4.1	1.9	1.8
Organic carbon (%)	0.88	0.60	0.46	23.3	26.6	20.2
CEC ($\text{Cmol (p}^+) \text{kg}^{-1}$)	14.8	11.9	10.6	-	-	-
Total lead (mg kg^{-1})	21.1	17.4	18.6	16.2	38.0	19.0

Table 2. Freundlich adsorption isotherms constants of lead adsorption on different soils of Aligarh in absence and presence of FYM, sewage and poultry litter

Soil	$K \pm s$	$1/n \pm s$	R^2
S ₁	72.5 ± 1.1	0.975 ± 0.005	0.97
S ₂	70.6 ± 1.3	0.96 ± 0.005	0.98
S ₃	68.4 ± 1.1	0.94 ± 0.01	0.97
S ₄	64.2 ± 1.5	0.93 ± 0.004	0.99
S ₅	64.1 ± 1.3	0.915 ± 0.005	0.96
S ₆	61.6 ± 1.6	0.900 ± 0.01	0.95
S ₇	60.1 ± 1.3	0.885 ± 0.005	0.97
S ₈	58.2 ± 1.1	0.865 ± 0.005	0.96
S ₉	61.4 ± 1.2	0.855 ± 0.005	0.97
S ₁₀	58.7 ± 1.0	0.840 ± 0.005	0.99
S ₁₁	56.3 ± 1.1	0.825 ± 0.005	0.98
S ₁₂	55.2 ± 1.2	0.815 ± 0.01	0.95

(±s - Standard error of estimation)

S₁-S₄ = Soil 1 amended with sewage sludge, FYM, poultry litter and unamended soil, respectively.

S₅-S₈ = Soil 2 amended with sewage sludge, FYM, poultry litter and unamended soil, respectively.

S₉-S₁₂ = Soil 3 amended with sewage sludge, FYM, poultry litter and unamended soil, respectively.

values are given in Table 2.

The value of $1/n$ during adsorption of lead was found to be less than unity indicating a convex or 'L' type of isotherm as defined by Giles *et al.*⁶. This kind of isotherm may arise from minimum competition of solvent for sites on the adsorbing surface. The slope of the isotherms (Fig. 1) steadily decreased with the rise in equilibrium (solute) concentration, since vacant sites became less accessible due to progressive adsorption⁷. Adsorption of lead followed the order : soil 1 > soil 2 > soil 3, which may be correlated with soil CEC, soil organic matter and clay content^{8,9}. A strong positive correlation ($r = 0.932$ to 0.964) was observed between lead adsorption on one hand, and soil CEC, soil organic matter and clay content of soil on the other and there was a statistically significant positive correlation between organic carbon and CEC of soils, CEC and clay content of soil.

The adsorption of lead on soil was noted to be relatively more in organic material-amended soil, and followed the order : sewage sludge > FYM > poultry litter > unamended soil. It may be due to interaction of Pb^{2+} with negatively charged organic matter, introduced to soil by adding different organic material as shown in the following scheme.

Fig. 1. Effect of organic material on lead adsorption, 1-4 soil : 1 amended with sewage sludge, FYM, poultry litter and unamended, 5-8 soil : 2 amended with sewage sludge, FYM, poultry litter and unamended, 9-12 soil : 3 amended with sewage sludge, FYM, poultry litter and unamended.

The Freundlich constants K and $1/n$ which provide rough estimates of the adsorbent capacity and intensity of adsorption, respectively were in the order : sewage sludge > FYM > poultry litter > unamended soil (Table 2) for lead adsorption by the given soils. These data denote that the adsorption capacity of soil at unit equilibrium concentration of lead increased with the addition of organic matter.

Desorption of lead : The data for amount of lead desorption from different soils amended with organic materials are given in Fig. 2. The amount of lead desorbed by water was relatively less than that by $0.002 M CaCl_2$. The desorption was 15–29% in presence of water, while 25–43% (of the adsorbed Pb) in presence of $0.002 M CaCl_2$. The amount and percentage desorption of lead increased with the increase of lead in equilibrium solution. Higher desorption of lead in presence of $0.002 M CaCl_2$ may be due to the fact that some of lead, bound loosely or precipitated, was extracted by $CaCl_2$. Similar results were also reported by Narwal and Singh¹⁰ and Sidhu *et al.*¹¹. The desorption followed the order : soil 3 > 2 > 1 which may be correlated to soil CEC and Pb

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Fig. 2

contd. (next page)

Fig. 2. Percentage of lead desorbed from different soils.

retention capacity of soil clay. The percentage of desorption in unamended soil was more than that in organic material amended soil, and followed the order : unamended > poultry litter > FYM > sewage sludge, thereby suggesting that incorporated organic material adversely affected desorption due to less lead availability and its more retention.

The step down multilinear functions between amount of lead adsorbed on soil and soil organic matter; percentage clay content revealed that the organic matter and the clay content were the most important factors influencing the lead adsorption by the present soils. The results could be quantified as follows : $Y = 176.5X + 64.3$; $Y = 11.2b + 31.3$; where Y = maximum amount of lead adsorbed; X = amount of soil organic carbon; b = percent clay content. With the help of these regression equations, it was found that there was a statistically significant positive correlation between lead adsorption and soil organic matter ($r = 0.999$) and lead adsorption and percent clay content ($r = 0.912$). There was also a positive correlation in between the amount of organic material-amended and amount of lead adsorbed ($r = 0.983$).

From these studies it may be concluded that organic matter and clay content were the major factors responsible for lead adsorption on soils and the lead adsorbed by organic material-amended soils may be retained for a long period in the soils. This may decrease the availability of Pb to crop grown on such soils, while preventing leaching of Pb through soil profile and its accumulation in the ground water.

Material and methods :

Three surface soils (0–30 cm; 1 to 3) from different parts of Aligarh district were collected and sieved through 100 mesh sieve. These soils were amended with FYM, sewage sludge and poultry litter, @ 5 g kg⁻¹ on organic carbon basis, and mixed thoroughly. The physico-chemical properties of soil and organic materials are given in Table 1.

Adsorption experiments were conducted by taking soil samples (10 g) (unamended and amended with organic material) in a large number of stoppered conical flasks adding various amounts of lead solution (0–15 mL of 2500 µg mL⁻¹ in 0.002 M CaCl₂) and making up the volume to 250 mL with distilled water. The samples were

then shaken for 24 h in a shaker. The samples were centrifuged for five minutes at 3000 rpm. Lead concentration in supernatant was estimated by atomic absorption spectrophotometer. The amount of Pb adsorbed was obtained from the amount added minus that left in the supernatant.

Desorption studies were conducted in two sets. In the first set 100 mL of distilled water and in second set 100 mL of 0.002 M CaCl₂ were added to soil residue left after centrifugation and samples were shaken for 24 h in a shaker. Supernatant was centrifuged at 3000 rpm and the amount of lead desorbed was estimated in the aliquots.

All the experiments were conducted in triplicate with suitable blanks.

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